

LANGUAGE TEACHING FOR MEDICAL PURPOSES

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The overall development has created a 'global' society where people from various linguistic backgrounds are connected with the aim of further progress and specialization. Society is now at a stage at which it is possible to obtain information about almost anything within a very short period. Such a situation requires the usage of one language for mutual understanding and communication of scientific, technological and academic information among different linguistic groups within a multi-linguistic community. Due to its influence and widespread usage, English has become the common language of international experts in a wide range of subjects, such as medicine, the natural sciences and the social sciences. Consequently, the language teaching profession has seen the emergence of language teaching for specific purposes. As technological and transportation advances have created a "global" society, that globalization has brought many professions and vocations into the international domain. The sub-field of English for Specific Purposes has emerged out of the field of English as a Second Language to meet the specific academic and professional needs of learners. Courses in ESP focus on the specific vocabulary and the unique language skills those in a given field are likely to require. English for specific purposes is closely connected to language for professional purposes, where speakers of English as a foreign or second language have to learn how to use language in areas where they are going to work. A major interest in this approach is to create knowledge about the specific needs to be covered in specialized language classrooms, in order to make this kind of language teaching as efficient as possible. The general effect of all this development was to exert pressure on the language teaching profession to deliver the required goods. Whereas English had previously decided its own destiny, it now became subject to the wishes, needs and demands of people other than language teachers (Hutchinson & Waters, 1987). The study of languages for specific purposes represents a synthesis of linguistics and methodology of teaching foreign languages. The study of languages for specific purposes (LSP) is highly student – centered, focused on learners' professional linguistic needs, as well as teaching materials production. In learner – centered approaches, course design and teaching often become negotiated, dynamic processes, since needs, expectations and student resources vary with each group. This suggests that LSP teachers must take into account student learning styles, strategies and language processing approaches. LSP teachers should assist students in becoming more flexible and more aware of their own learning styles and approaches. Need analysis English for Specific Purposes focuses on the learner and one of the greatest contributions of teaching English for Specific Purposes is the emphasis it puts on the thorough analysis of the students' needs when designing the course. The analysis includes an assessment of the current level of knowledge students possess and determining the target situation, what the student wants to achieve. The teaching staff and students of the Faculty of Medicine, University of Nis agree that knowledge of both General English and English for medical purposes are necessary for progress and development in science Antic and workplace. For this reason, knowledge of General English at an intermediate level is mandatory for a successful participation in the course. An overall needs analysis shows that students need training in specialized language, which includes not only vocabulary but also specific grammatical structures, phrases, styles and principles of oral and written communication, which are characteristic for medical profession. The information obtained from needs analysis can be used to help define program goals. These goals can then be stated as specific teaching

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objectives, which in turn will function as the foundation on which to develop lesson plans, materials, tests, assignments and activities. Basically, a need analysis will help to clarify the purposes of the teaching program. Authenticity – ESP and real world work situations In ESP, the authentic world must be brought to the students, and they must learn to interact with the language as it is spoken and written in target situation. Thus, ESP teachers must be willing to negotiate with both experts in the target situation and with the students. Even though there are many textbooks believed to be appropriate for ESP courses, Johns (1981) claims that no textbook can fulfill all demands of a specific situation. For this reason, the teacher must rely on his/her own knowledge when assessing the appropriateness of the material to be used for developing students' skills. The material, which is used at English for Medical Purposes course, includes authentic texts, parts of General English and ESP textbooks, materials prepared by the teacher and topics and tasks related to the field of medicine. Good material contains interesting texts, thought – provoking activities, enables students to use knowledge and skills they possess. A clear and coherent material structure will help the teacher in designing the course and it will help the students in achieving the sense of progress and accomplishment. The course designed in accordance with the modern ESP methodology will enhance peer work and teamwork and it will enable shared learning. Various authors have suggested conducting ESP courses as close to the workplace as possible. Crandall (1984) suggested making the classroom into a simulated workplace in order to integrate the language and the "specific purposes." The workplace context also helps keep the focus more on the specific purposes and less on the language.

Both learners and teachers are accustomed to a high degree of teacher control and they cannot imagine what a class may look like without it. Teachers may find it difficult to motivate the learners to work independently – young people do not feel truly responsible for their own learning. Students may have deeply rooted beliefs about the roles of teachers and students, which may slow down the process of achieving independent learning. It is crucial to show students the range of autonomous options and raise their awareness of the different learning strategies that are open to them. Students need to take responsibility for their own language development, which would in turn prove useful when the students have to use English in their professional lives. Students have different individual needs for their professional lives. The majority have learnt to over – rely on teachers in their language learning careers. There is a need to prepare the students for self – directed learning outside the classroom to acquire the habit of learning continuously. The English teachers at the Faculty of Medicine usually have less medical knowledge that learners therefore are perceived as lay people as opposed to 'expert' students. Since students usually transfer their knowledge of medical subjects onto the English course, they can help in planning the course itself, which enables the development of student autonomy.

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